

FEATURES OF FOOTBALL AND ITS PLACE IN THE SYSTEM PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article discusses the features of football as a sport and its place in the system of physical education. The physical and psychological aspects of playing football are analyzed, as well as the role of this sport in the development of motor skills, coordination and teamwork. Methods of teaching and training in football are discussed, as well as the importance of its inclusion in the general physical education program for the development of physical qualities and the formation of a healthy lifestyle.

Keywords: football, sports games, physical development, education, youth, training, team sports, healthy lifestyle, socialization, coordination of movements, competitions.

Football is the most accessible and therefore mass means of physical education and health promotion for the general population. Football attracts people with its entertainment value, abundance of various technical and tactical techniques, emotionality, dynamism, both collectivism and individualism, and besides, according to many experts, it is the most effective means for comprehensive physical development.

By the way, football is perhaps the only popular sport whose date and place of origin are known for certain. More than a dozen books have been written about this significant event, often telling in fictitious detail about the first steps of this future addiction of millions.

The popularity of football and its widespread use in the system of physical education are determined, first of all, by the economic accessibility of the game, high emotionality, great spectacular effect, complex effects on the body and education of youth.

Football is based on natural movements - walking, stopping, turning, jumping, passing, dribbling and hitting the goal, carried out in single combat with opponents. They are easy to teach to children, teenagers and adults. Therefore, football is included in the education and training program for children, starting from kindergartens, and games with swords - from the age of two.

The desire to surpass an opponent in the speed of action aimed at achieving victory teaches those involved to mobilize all their capabilities, act with maximum effort, and overcome the difficulties that develop during sports wrestling. These features contribute to the development of perseverance, determination and determination. A varied alternation of movements and actions, often varying in intensity and duration, has an overall complex effect on the body of those involved. Playing football contributes to the development of basic physical qualities, the formation of various motor skills and the strengthening of internal organs.

The variety of technical and tactical actions of playing football and especially gaming activities have unique properties for the formation of vital skills and abilities of those involved in football, the comprehensive development of their physical, technical, tactical and mental

qualities. Mastered motor actions of playing football and physical exercises associated with it are effective means of promoting health and can be used by a person throughout his life in independent forms of physical education. Football has become widespread throughout the world; interest in this sport is growing every year, and competition in the international arena is intensifying. The latter makes it necessary to improve the methods of sports training and education, taking into account the development trends of football.

Modern football is one of the most dynamic sports games. This determines the main trends in its development. Firstly, the constant desire to improve playing technique and bring it to the level of virtuosity, which makes a great impression on athletes as a psychological factor. Secondly, there is a constant trend towards increasing the level of athletic preparedness of players. Thirdly, wittingly or unwittingly, the game in modern (professional) football occurs in such a way that, as a rule, none of the teams can achieve a large advantage in the score. All this indicates the need for constant functional and intellectual development of the player, his mental activity, perfect reaction, correct movement, and the ability to navigate in constantly changing situations (M. A. Godik, N.Ya. Petrov, R. Akramov, etc.). The technique and tactics of playing football are varied. The technique of playing football consists of two main sections: the technique of playing in attack and the technique of playing in defense.

The technical skill of a football player is characterized by the number of techniques he masters, the variety of their implementation and the ability to perform these techniques with active opposition. The modern football player is characterized by the universalism of technical and tactical skill, manifested in the ability to master all techniques of attack and defense, and especially those that are most characteristic of his function in the team.

Objectives and content of the educational and training process in football.

In the process of sports training, football players develop skills and abilities. This is achieved by repeated repetition of exercises, which, in turn, affect the activity of all organs and systems. Sports training is the targeted use of the entire set of factors (means, methods, conditions), which together ensure the football player's readiness for sports achievements.

Organized football classes are designed to solve the problems facing the physical education system. The main content of classes should be the harmonious improvement of a person, the comprehensive development of his spiritual and physical abilities.

However, in the pursuit of high sports results in football practice, the health-improving orientation of education and training and their educational nature are sometimes forgotten. Such a one-sided approach to training. As a rule, it leads to sad consequences.

The main basis for mastering football skills is excellent health, development, and high moral and volitional qualities.

In the process of teaching and training football players, the following tasks are solved:

- a) Improving motor skills and volitional qualities,
- b) Expanding the functional capabilities of athletes' bodies (respiratory, cardiovascular and other systems)
- c) Preservation and improvement of sports performance,
- d) expanding knowledge in the field of sports and instilling hygiene and self-control skills;
- e) Fostering hard work, discipline, consciousness, and activity
- f) Developing the right attitude towards the opponent, judges and spectators.

Consistently solving these problems during the training process allows you to more fully use the colossal capabilities of the human body to achieve high sports results.

The continuous growth of the level of skill of rival teams makes it necessary to annually increase the requirements for all aspects of training

football players. The positive impact of increased requirements for the training of football players is ensured through the consistent implementation of the principles of training, and first of all, strict adherence to the laws of scientific management of its process. Achieving sports results in football depends on the level of general and specialty preparedness of the player. Each student must have high motor potential, allowing him to begin systematic sports training. On the basis of general preparedness, specialized training is built that meets the specifics of football. The complex nature of the motor manifestations of players requires versatile special training of those involved. In football, its scope is especially wide, since individual qualities and skills require special skills and abilities for collective interaction. Each player, in addition to general game training, acquires the knowledge, qualities and skills necessary to perform certain functions in the team.

Special studies (Ts. Zheleznyakov, V. Yanov, K. Popov) have proven the influence of performing various game functions. It manifests itself both in perceptual processes (in the processing of information), and with the development of special physical qualities, when mastering technology - tactical techniques.

Modern trends in the development of football, expressed in the intensification of game actions, increasing their effectiveness, expanding the arsenal of techniques, increase the requirements for the level of training of football players. Our universities especially require fundamental knowledge of the content of the game, training systems, flexibility and highly automated skills and perfect functioning of the functional systems of the body. Each type of training solves its own problems and, together with others, ensures the achievement of general and special tasks of the educational and training process. At the same time, they are all closely related to each other.

All types of preparation form the structure of the educational and training process in football. It is based on intellectual, organizational and methodological preparation. Then comes psychological preparation. The next place is occupied by physical training, which creates the basis for the implementation of special knowledge and skills. The central place in the structure of the educational and training process belongs to technical and tactical training, during which special playing techniques of football players are studied. Each of these types, in one form or another, is necessarily included in the educational and training process of those involved in football. However, the specific weight, and most importantly, the content, changes at various stages of long-term preparation. Thus, in playing football with children, the share of physical training increases, ensuring the full development of the body. In teams of qualified athletes, the main attention is paid to technical and tactical preparation for participation in competitions

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